

**ERK2 drives MYC expression acting as a kinase-independent anchor for CDK9
at the MYC promoter**

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ABSTRACT

ERK1/2 Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinases can bind to DNA and modify gene expression. In this line, we have investigated whether ERK could directly regulate *MYC* transcription. Bioinformatic analyses unveiled an overrepresentation of ERK binding sites in the *MYC* promoter. Consistently, chromatin immunoprecipitation revealed the presence of ERK2 thereat in serum-stimulated cells. Consequently, we found that ERK2 recruitment to the *MYC* promoter was sufficient to upregulate *MYC* mRNA and protein levels, in a kinase-independent fashion. Noticeably, we show that ERK2 coincides with CDK9 at the *MYC* promoter. In this respect, we demonstrate that ERK2 can bind to CDK9 via its CD domain. This interaction does not affect CDK9 kinase activity but it is essential for ERK2-induced *MYC* induction since CDK9 depletion precludes it. Remarkably, artificially tethering CDK9 to the *MYC* promoter by fusing an ERK2 insert domain to its C-terminus is sufficient to drive *MYC* expression. Overall, our results unveil an unprecedented role for ERK, acting as a kinase-independent anchor for the recruitment of CDK9 to the *MYC* promoter in order to regulate *MYC* expression.

AUTHOR SUMMARY

ERK1/2 Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinases can directly bind to DNA and regulate gene expression by not fully understood mechanisms. In this study, we have detected the presence of ERK2 at the *MYC* promoter, where it coincides with CDK9, the main activator of RNA polymerase II in order to drive transcription. We have found that ERK2 can drive *MYC* expression independently of its kinase activity by a novel mechanism. Our results demonstrate that ERK2 binds to CDK9 and recruits it to the *MYC* promoter acting as a kinase-independent anchor, in order to promote *MYC* expression. As such, our findings unveil an unprecedented role for ERK beyond its canonical kinase functions, serving as a tether for transcriptional activators at promoters.

INTRODUCTION

MYC is one of the most prevalent oncogenes in human cancer as it is found deregulated in roughly half of the human tumors. In cancer, *MYC* gene expression is often deregulated through diverse mechanisms including: stabilizing mutations, chromosomal translocation, gene amplification and transcriptional upregulation (1, 2). Among these, *MYC* transcriptional overexpression is the most frequent, and, as a consequence, many tumors display elevated MYC activity in the absence of translocations or amplifications (3, 4). Likewise, it is well known that different types of cells, such as lymphocytes and fibroblasts, exhibit a dramatic up-regulation of MYC mRNA levels when cells are induced to exit quiescence upon stimulation with serum or growth factors like LPA and EGF (5-8). However, despite the time elapsed, a detailed knowledge of the processes unfolding at the *MYC* promoter, responsible for the regulation of *MYC* transcriptional output, both under physiological and pathological settings, is largely missing.

Activation of RNA polymerase II (Pol II hereafter) is the hallmark of gene transcription. Pol II is fully activated by phosphorylation on critical residues, serine 2 and serine 5, within the heptapeptide repeats in its carboxy-terminal domain (CTD hereafter) (9). Such process is catalyzed by the positive transcription elongation factor b (P-TEFb) that is composed of the cyclin-dependent kinase CDK9 and its regulatory partners: cyclin T1 (CycT1) or its minor forms T2a and T2b (10, 11). Activation of P-TEFb is a complex process, orchestrated at multiple levels. In mammalian cells, about half of P-TEFb is present in large inactive complexes. The balance of active and inactive P-TEFb is tightly controlled and it can change dramatically in response to external cues such as growth factor stimulation (12). P-TEFb activity requires phosphorylation of CDK9, an event that is modulated post-recruitment to promoters in order to prevent premature CTD phosphorylation (13). CDK9 contains an activation loop that must be phosphorylated in order to unleash its activity, a task undertaken by CDK7 (14). In addition, other kinases also participate in P-TEFb activation by yet unknown

mechanisms. For example, signals mediated by Extracellular-Regulated Kinase 1/2 (ERK, hereafter) have been shown to favor the assembly of cyclinT1-CDK9 heterodimers, facilitating the recruitment of P-TEFb to actively transcribed genes (15) by not fully understood mechanisms.

ERK1/2 Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinases play a pivotal role in the conveyance of external stimuli-generated signals to the nucleus, where they switch-on genetic programs necessary for cellular proliferation, differentiation and survival, in addition to hundreds of cell- and tissue-specific processes (16, 17). It is well documented that the regulation of gene expression by ERK is achieved primarily through activation, via direct phosphorylation, of a broad array of transcription factors (18, 19), including MYC (20) (21). However, evidence has mounted showing that ERK can also regulate gene expression independently of its kinase activity (22). For example, by triggering the release of retinoblastoma (RB) from its inactive state when bound to laminA (23). In addition, new twists have been added by findings pointing to ERK as a direct regulator of chromatin architecture (24-26), and showing that ERK can bind to DNA directly (27) and localize in the promoter regions of genes (28). In this line, herein we show that ERK sits at the *MYC* promoter region and regulates *MYC* expression in an unprecedented mode by, in a kinase-independent fashion, binding to and recruiting CDK9 to the *MYC* promoter, fostering its transcriptional activity therein.

RESULTS

ERK2 binds to the *MYC* promoter

We sought to investigate whether ERK plays a role in the regulation of transcription at the *MYC* promoter. Since it has been shown that ERK binds to DNA at a defined motif: C/GAAAG/C (27), we performed bioinformatic analyses in order to reveal the presence of these ERK binding sites (ERK boxes) in a set of mammalian *MYC* promoters. ERK boxes were common in the mouse, rat and human promoters, but only some of these boxes were conserved among the different species (Fig. 1A). ERK boxes were more numerous in the promoters of genes of the *MYC* complex than in those regulating genes of the RAS-ERK pathway (Supp Fig. S1A). Chromatin immunoprecipitation experiments (ChIP) were then performed to evaluate ERK recruitment to *MYC* promoter regions containing ERK boxes, in human 293T cells and mouse embryo fibroblasts (MEFs). In both cases, the presence of ERK was detected at the promoter regions with conserved ERK boxes, more prominently at those regions with the highest number of boxes. Noticeably, ERK binding increased significantly in response to EGF or serum stimulation (Fig. 1B, C and Supp Fig. S1B). In this respect, in HeLa cells it has been shown that ERK2 associates to chromatin following interferon gamma (IFN γ) treatment (27). Thus, we tested if ERK bound to the *MYC* promoter under such stimulus, and found that the presence of ERK at the regions with ERK boxes was markedly augmented upon treatment with IFN γ (Fig. 1D). In addition, we investigated ERK binding to the *MYC* promoter in response to oncogenic RAS signals. To this end, we used rat pheochromocytoma UR61 cells that harbor a dexamethasone-inducible NRAS^{Q61} oncogene (29). As shown in Figure 1E, NRAS signals triggered ERK activation and nuclear translocation (Supp Fig. S1C) and its subsequent tethering to the *MYC* promoter regions containing ERK boxes. Altogether, these data demonstrate that diverse stimuli evoke ERK recruitment to the *MYC* promoter.

Nuclear ERK induces synthesis of MYC mRNA and protein

Next, we asked whether ERK binding to the *MYC* promoter unleashed gene expression. Stimulation of quiescent NIH3T3 cells with serum readily induced *MYC* mRNA and protein synthesis, an effect that was completely abolished by treatment with the MEK inhibitor U0126 (Fig 2A) or the ERK kinase inhibitor SCH772984 (Supp Fig. S2A), thereby suggesting ERK participation in such process. To further substantiate this finding, we took advantage of a line of MEFs, knock-out for *ERK1* and harboring a floxed *ERK2* plus a 4-hydroxy-tamoxifen (4-HT)-inducible Cre recombinase (*ERK1*^{-/-}; *ERK2*^{lox/lox}; Cre-ER) (30). Addition of 4-HT to proliferating MEFs resulted in the gradual acquisition of an “ERK-less” phenotype, upon the loss of *ERK2*, fully apparent after 9 days of treatment. Noticeably, a drop on Myc protein levels was observed concomitantly with the reduction of ERK expression (Fig. 2B). Likewise, after 9 days of treatment with 4-HT, *MYC* mRNA synthesis in response to EGF stimulation was significantly reduced compared to vehicle-treated MEFs (Fig. 2C). These results demonstrated that ERK is a critical factor for the induction of *MYC* expression upon mitogenic stimulation.

In its promoter, *MYC* harbors elements responsive to transcription factors phosphorylated/activated by ERK upon serum stimulation (31, 32) (Supp Fig. S2B). In this respect, we wanted to ascertain the importance of ERK nuclear translocation for *MYC* regulation. To this end, we used an ERK2 construct harboring a supplementary Nuclear Localization Signal (ERK-NLS hereafter) capable of translocating to the nucleus in the absence of mitogenic stimulation (23). We also utilized ERK2 mutant forms for the SPS domain, involved in ERK nuclear translocation. Namely, the EPE mutant, constitutively found in the nucleus, and the APA mutant, impaired for nuclear translocation (33)(Supp Fig. S2C). It was found that both ERK-NLS and EPE efficiently induced *MYC* expression in quiescent cells to levels even higher than those evoked by ERK2 wild-type, known to translocate to the nucleus when overexpressed (34). By contrast, the APA mutant failed to do so (Fig. 2D),

thereby demonstrating that ERK nuclear translocation is essential for the regulation of *MYC* expression. It was important to discriminate to which extent *MYC* gene expression was due to ERK direct action, as opposed to being triggered by other ERK-activated transcriptional events following agonist stimulation. In this sense, it was found that ERK-NLS readily induced *MYC* protein expression in quiescent cells, in which ERK-inducible transcription factors like ELK1 were unphosphorylated (Fig. 2E). These results demonstrated that the sole presence of nuclear ERK was sufficient to induce *MYC* expression under conditions in which ERK-dependent transcription factors were not active. Thus, pointing to ERK direct interaction with the *MYC* promoter as the trigger for *MYC* expression.

It was of interest to determine which ERK boxes were critical for *MYC* induction. To this end, we used a set of luciferase reporter constructs under the control of different fragments of the *MYC* promoter, which were co-transfected with ERK-NLS in HeLa cells. Our results indicated that the fragment containing two conserved ERK boxes mapping at -1 kb (Frag B) was sufficient for full activation of the *MYC* promoter by ERK-NLS under quiescence conditions. To ascertain this point, we generated a construct in which both of the conserved ERK boxes were deleted (Fragment B1D2), something that rendered this construct unresponsive to stimulation by ERK-NLS (Fig. 2F), demonstrating that ERK activated the *MYC* promoter through such ERK boxes. It is noteworthy that, according to the ChIP-seq data released by the ENCODE project (www.encodeproject.org), a binding site for ELK1 is present in the B1D2 fragment, (Supp Fig 2B), which is unable to activate transcription in response to the presence of ERK2. Further supporting the notion that, in this context, ERK-driven *MYC* expression is independent of ERK-responsive transcription factors.

ERK binds to CDK9

We desired to unveil the mechanism whereby nuclear ERK activated *MYC* expression. CDK9 is the catalytic component of P-TEFb, responsible for phosphorylating the CTD of RNA pol II to promote the transition from a paused state to productive elongation of transcription (35). CDK9 also phosphorylates RB (36), and we previously reported that ERK2 induces the phosphorylation of RB upon its release from lamin A via an unidentified kinase (23). This hinted for a functional connection between CDK9 and ERK, so we asked if ERK and CDK9 could interact. Indeed, coimmunoprecipitation experiments in 293T cells demonstrated that nuclear ERK2 bound to endogenous CDK9 but not to other CDKs like CDK7 and CDK8 (Fig. 3A). To visualize how endogenous ERK2 and CDK9 interacted in live cells we performed proximity ligation assays (PLA) in HeLa cells, which revealed that endogenous ERK2 and CDK9 complexed, whereas ERK2 did not bind to CDK2. This interaction took place primarily in the nucleus, though some ERK2-CDK9 binding was also apparent in the cytoplasm, where both proteins are known to reside as well (Supp Fig. S3A), and it increased in response to EGF stimulation (Fig. 3B; Supp Fig. S3B). Next, we went on to determine how different functional forms of ERK2 interacted with CDK9. We found that CDK9 associated with nuclear ERK2 wild-type just as efficiently as with a kinase-deficient mutant K52R (DK) (37) and with an unphosphorylatable ERK2 form (AEF) (38), indicating that ERK2 kinase activity is not a requirement in order to bind CDK9. Likewise, ERK1 was also found to interact with CDK9 (Fig. 3C).

We then wanted to identify the regions of CDK9 involved in its interaction with ERK2. For this purpose, a set of deletion mutants of CDK9 fused to GST were generated, purified from bacteria and used as baits to pull-down ERK from lysates of 293T cells. Noticeably, two regions of CDK9, those spanning amino acids 1-100 and 264-333, were capable of interacting with ERK (Fig. 4A). We noticed that both regions contained consensus ERK-binding domains. Specifically, amino acids 1-100 harbored a D-domain, whereas the region spanning amino acids 264-33 contained an FXF domain

(39). We then disabled these domains by substituting critical residues for alanine (Supp Fig. S4A) in order to generate CDK9 mutants with defective ERK binding sites. It was found that CDK9 FM, a mutant harboring a non-functional FXF domain, retained its ability to interact with ERK in coimmunoprecipitation assays (Fig. 4B). Interestingly, PLA showed that disruption of the FXF domain dramatically altered CDK9 cellular sublocalization from nuclear to cytoplasmic, even carrying with itself nuclear ERK-NLS to the cytoplasm (Supp Fig. S4B). Conversely, ERK2-CDK9 interaction was completely impaired when a mutation disrupting the D-domain, CDK9 FDM, was introduced (Fig. 4B; Supp Fig. S4B). In the same vein, we found that an ERK2 deletion mutant comprising its insert region (Δ Ins) (40), through which it binds FXF domains, retained its capacity for associating to CDK9 (Fig. 4C). Contrarily, the mutant D319N, impaired for binding D-domains (41), failed to interact with CDK9 (Fig. 4C). As a consequence, its ability to transactivate the *MYC* promoter was markedly impaired (Fig. 4D). All together, these results demonstrated that ERK binds to CDK9 mainly through the D-domain.

In consonance, we next investigated the functional consequences of ERK-CDK9 interaction. For this, we evaluated the phosphorylation of Pol II CTD at Ser 2, the hallmark of CDK9 activation (42). Expression of ERK-NLS in serum-starved 293T cells markedly stimulated CTD phosphorylation. However, this did not occur when CDK9 expression levels were down-regulated by siRNA (Fig. 4E), pointing to CDK9, not ERK, as the kinase phosphorylating CTD. To further substantiate this finding, we asked whether ERK could potentiate CDK9 kinase activity. To this end, we performed in vitro CDK9 kinase assays using purified proteins. Remarkably, we found that incubation of CDK9 with ERK2, or its mutant forms, did not affect CDK9 capacity for phosphorylating CTD (Fig. 4F) indicating that, at least in vitro, ERK does not bolster CDK9 kinase activity. Overall, these results demonstrate that ERK binds to CDK9 and promotes CDK9-mediated CTD phosphorylation, but does not stimulate CDK9 kinase activity.

ERK induces *MYC* expression via CDK9

Once the association between ERK and CDK9 had been ascertained, we asked whether such interaction was necessary for ERK-induced *MYC* gene expression. It was found that partial silencing of CDK9 expression using siRNAs was sufficient to significantly curtail the upregulation of *MYC* mRNA and protein levels evoked by ERK2-NLS expression (Fig. 5A). Also, in the CDK9-silenced cells, we observed that serum-induced *MYC* mRNA levels were significantly attenuated compared to parental cells (Fig. 5B). In these CDK9-knocked-down cells, *MYC* protein expression was restored when CDK9 expression was rescued by the transfection of an ectopic CDK9 wild-type. This was also the case when cells were transfected with the CDK9 FM mutant. By contrast, when cells were transfected with the CDK9 FDM mutant, unable to bind ERK, *MYC* protein levels remained low (Fig. 5C). These results demonstrated that the induction of *MYC* expression by ERK was mediated by CDK9.

Since we had observed that ERK2, independently of its activation state, could bind to CDK9 we also tested whether the aforementioned ERK mutants defective for phospho-transfer activity were capable of evoking *MYC* gene expression. Interestingly, both ERK2 DK and ERK2 AEF were as capable as the wild-type form of inducing *MYC* mRNA synthesis (Fig. 5D) and protein expression (Fig. 5E) under quiescence conditions. Altogether, these results indicate that the CDK9-ERK interaction is critical for the up-regulation of *MYC* expression and that such effect is independent on ERK kinase activity.

ERK tethers CDK9 to the *MYC* promoter

The above results strongly suggested that ERK recruitment to the *MYC* promoter was sufficient to induce CDK9 activation and *MYC* transcriptional activity. Conceptually, this would

require that ERK and CDK9 coincided on the *MYC* promoter chromatin. To put this notion under test, we performed CHIP assays using antibodies against ERK and CDK9 to scan the human *MYC* promoter and 3' downstream regions lacking ERK boxes (Supp Fig. S5A) for locations where ERK and CDK9 co-localized. In two different cell lines, HeLa and 293T, initial results unveiled that ERK2 and CDK9 extensively co-localized around the -1kb region (Supp Fig. S5B), the position where the conserved ERK boxes previously found to drive ERK-dependent *MYC* expression were located (Fig 1A, Fig 2F, Supp Fig S2B). Additional analyses in HeLa cells confirmed that indeed this was the case (Fig 6A). To further confirm these findings we used the ERK-less MEFs. As previously shown in Figure 2B, in these cells 4-HT treatment resulted in total ERK elimination, as a consequence of which the presence of CDK9 at the aforementioned *Myc* promoter region was completely lost (Fig 6B). Accordingly, ERK depletion resulted in the stalling of Pol II at the *Myc* promoter, impeding its progression (Supp Fig. S5C). These results indicated that ERK and CDK9 colocalized at the *MYC* promoter in a critical region for its transcription and that ERK is essential for CDK9 binding to the *MYC* promoter.

Since it has been shown that ERK can directly bind to DNA via its insert region (27), we asked whether this would be necessary to drive *MYC* expression. It was found that, unlike wild-type ERK2, a deletion mutant lacking its insert region (Δ Ins) was incapable of inducing *MYC* mRNA and protein expression (Fig. 7A). Since, as shown above (Fig. 4C), ERK does not require its insert region for binding to CDK9, we reasoned that such region should be participating in ERK binding to DNA within the *MYC* promoter. In light of this data, we envisioned that in order to drive *MYC* expression ERK would be serving as a tether for CDK9 at the *MYC* promoter by binding to DNA through its insert region. To validate such hypothesis, we generated a chimeric construct in which ERK2 insert region was fused to CDK9 at its C-terminus (CDK9^{ins}) and tested its ability to drive *MYC* expression, by luciferase assays. It was found that the addition of ERK2 insert region was sufficient to bolster the

ability of CDK9 for inducing *MYC* expression under serum starvation conditions (Fig. 7B). Likewise, CDK9^{ins} proved more efficient than CDK9 wild-type for rescuing *MYC* expression in HeLa cell with knocked-down endogenous CDK9 (Fig. 7C). However, both constructs accelerated the growth rate of proliferating NIH3T3 cells to similar levels (Fig. 7D), probably due to endogenous ERK levels being sufficiently elevated so as to efficiently tether CDK9 wild-type to the *MYC* promoter, to yield a robust mitogenic response. In summary, all the above results demonstrate that ERK evokes *MYC* expression by facilitating CDK9 recruitment to the *MYC* promoter, acting as a kinase-independent tether therein.

DISCUSSION

It has been known for more than thirty years that the induction of *MYC* gene expression is a hallmark of mitogenic stimulation in quiescent cells. Our current data provides evidence directly connecting ERK with the transcriptional machinery that unleashes *MYC* expression. The necessity of ERK for the induction of *MYC* expression by specific mitogens (43) or by RAS/RAF signals (44) is well established. However, in these processes the role played by ERK has been solely associated with its kinase activity and the resulting phosphorylation/activation of a set of transcription factors necessary for triggering gene expression (18, 19). While there is no question that this is a central mechanism whereby ERK regulates gene transcription in general, here we demonstrate that ERK unphosphorylated mutant forms and/or deprived of phospho-transfer activity are competent for driving *MYC* expression.

Of course, ERK must be phosphorylated in order to translocate to the nucleus. However, our data showing that ERK can evoke *MYC* expression independently of its kinase activity implies that ERK-driven transcriptional activity could be maintained long after ERK has been dephosphorylated/deactivated by nuclear phosphatases and the activity of ERK-phosphorylated transcription factors has ceased. In this respect, it is noticeable that from the growing list of kinase-independent functions undertaken by ERK (22), the majority are nuclear events, such as: the activation of PARP-1 (45), topoisomerase II (46), MKP3 (47) and Rb (23). Therefore, for a total switch-off of ERK nuclear functions, in addition to its dephosphorylation by phosphatases, an effective machinery for re-shuttling ERK to the cytoplasm must be active.

Our bioinformatic analyses have unveiled that ERK-binding DNA motifs (C/GAAAG/C) are highly conserved in mammalian *MYC* promoters and we have identified a subset of these ERK boxes

as essential for driving *MYC* expression. Remarkably, our data also indicates that ERK and CDK9 co-localize at these regions. In this vein, we demonstrate that ERK requires the participation of CDK9 in order to drive *MYC* expression, in agreement with previous reports showing that unleashing ERK activation promotes the assembly of functional CDK9 complexes at the promoters of active genes (15) to enhance transcription (48).

Furthermore, we show that both ERK1 and 2 can directly bind to CDK9 and that this interaction takes place primarily at the nucleus. Accordingly, in CDK9 we have unveiled the presence of ERK docking motifs, both FXF and D- domains. Our results indicate that ERK/CDK9 interaction takes place mainly through CDK9 D-domain binding to ERK CD domain; since the corresponding loss-of-function mutant forms, CDK9 FDM and ERK2 D316, are defective in their mutual association. Conversely, the disruption of CDK9 FXF domains does not prevent its binding to ERK, even though it dramatically alters its subcellular localization from nuclear to cytoplasmic. This is consistent with our results showing that unphosphorylatable ERK2 can still bind to CDK9, as the hydrophobic DEF/FRS pocket, the part of the insert region involved in binding to FXF domains, is formed only when ERK becomes dually phosphorylated (39). However, we show that the ERK2 Δ Ins mutant, though capable of associating to CDK9, is incompetent for inducing *MYC* expression. Considering that ERK binds to DNA by means of its insert region (27) we posit that ERK association to DNA through this region, would be necessary for anchoring CDK9, through ERK CD domain, to the *MYC* promoter (Fig. 8). Since, according to our data, ERK does not promote CDK9 kinase activity, we posit that an important role for ERK in the regulation of *MYC* transcription would be acting as a tether to facilitate CDK9 recruitment to the *MYC* promoter, a task that would not require ERK kinase activity nor being in a phosphorylated state, notwithstanding the fact that it must be phosphorylated in order to translocate to the nucleus. Noticeably, recent reports show that ERK can recruit repressors to the *Nanog* locus, impeding Pol II activation (49). These findings in combination with ours, suggest

that ERK can act as an anchor in promoters either to activate or repress transcription depending on its interacting partners.

Overall, for the past years, data has been accumulating pointing to a role for ERK in the control of gene transcription, via direct interaction with promoters and other regulatory regions (26-28, 50-52). Our results provide further mechanistic insights in this realm, underscoring ERK participation beyond its role as a kinase, in agreement with previous findings reporting the ability of kinase-inactive ERK mutants for binding DNA (53). Moreover, data have been accumulating pointing to CDK9 as a therapeutic target in MYC-driven tumors (54-57). In this vein, the results presented herein endorse such findings by unveiling the critical role played by CDK9, in association to ERK, as a central regulator of *MYC* expression.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Cell culture and transfections. 293T and HeLa cells were purchased from ATCC. NIH-3T3 cells and ERK-less MEFs were provided by Mariano Barbacid, CNIO (Madrid). 293T cells were transfected using Polyethylenimine (PEI, Polysciences, Inc.) 1 mg/mL in a 1:3 ratio w/w (DNA:PEI). Others were transfected using Lipofectamine LTX (Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher), following manufacturer's instructions. Descriptions for plasmid and siRNA reagents descriptions can be found in Supplemental Material and Methods.

RT-qPCR. RNA samples were purified using the RNA Isolation Kit (Nzytech) following manufacturer's instructions. 100 ng of RNA was reversed to complementary DNA using iScript cDNA Synthesis Kit (Bio-Rad). Between 5 to 10 ng of cDNA were used as template to perform qPCR with the SYBR® Select Master Mix (Applied Biosystems). qPCRs were carried out in a CFX Connect Real-Time PCR Detection System (Bio-Rad).

Immunoprecipitation and Western Blot Analyses. Performed essentially as described (58). Antibodies description can be found in Supplemental Material and Methods.

Recombinant protein purification. GST (Glutathione S-transferase)-tagged recombinant proteins (GST-CDK9 fragments) were expressed in *E. coli* BL21 strain. Protein expression was induced by the addition of 1 mM IPTG for 4 h at 37 °C. Quantitation of the obtained protein was performed by SDS-PAGE and staining with Coomassie blue, using a BSA standard.

Immunofluorescence. Cells were fixed with 4 % paraformaldehyde (PFA) for 10 min at RT and permeabilized with PBS-Triton 0.5 % for 30 min. Primary and secondary antibodies were incubated for 1 h and then washed twice with PBS 1X. Cells were visualized in a Zeiss IMAGER M1

fluorescence microscope/confocal microscope (Leica TCS SP5), using excitation wavelengths of 488 nm, 594 nm and 647nm. Images were analyzed with the ImageJ software.

Proximity Ligation Assays (PLA). Performed using Duolink® *in situ* Red Starter kit Mouse/Rabbit (Sigma-Aldrich) following manufacturer's instructions. Visualized in a Zeiss IMAGER M1 fluorescence microscope/confocal microscope (Leica TCS SP5), using excitation wavelengths of 488 nm, 594 nm and 647nm. Images were analyzed with the ImageJ software.

***In vitro* CDK9 kinase assays.** GST- ERK2 mutants and CTD, utilized as substrate, were affinity purified using glutathione beads from *E. coli* BL21. CDK9/CyclinK complex was purchased from Sigma. Kinase assays were performed following manufacturer's instructions. Samples were resolved by 12 % SDS-PAGE and detected by autoradiography using Konica films.

Luciferase Assays. The full MYC promoter or its portions as indicated in the different figures were cloned in the reporter plasmid pSG424 G5P2. These and the Renilla luciferase control plasmid were transfected in addition to the indicated constructs into 293T or HeLa cells. Luciferase activity was determined using the dual Luciferase Assay System (Promega). Results were normalized on the basis of the Renilla luciferase activity.

Chromatin immunoprecipitation. ChIP was performed by using magnetic beads coupled to the specific antibodies or IgGs as controls To reduce nonspecific background, Dynabeads were previously incubated with salmon sperm DNA. Chromatin was eluted and RNase was added followed by decrosslinking and Proteinase K (Roche) addition. DNA was purified using Qiaquick columns (Qiagen). For binding analyses RT-qPCR was performed using the suitable primers that can be found in Supplemental Material and Methods.

Cellular proliferation assay. 90 μ L of a 5000-cell suspension of NIH3T3 cells were seeded in 96-well plates 72 hours after transfection in triplicates. 10 μ L of PrestoBlue (Invitrogen A13261) were added to each well at room temperature and incubated for 3 hours at 37 °C. Afterwards, absorbance was measured at 570nm and 600nm.

Statistical analyses: data was processed and analyzed using the GraphPad Prism 7 Software (GraphPad Software, Inc., San Diego, CA). In bar graphs data is given as Mean \pm SD and Two tailed unpaired Student's t-test was used to determine differences between data sets and significance.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS.

Supplementary figures 1-6

Supplementary Experimental Procedures

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceptualization, PC, JL. Methodology, PC, JL, AM. Investigation, LA-I, MM, LG-G, AQ, JR. Validation, LA-I, MM. Formal Analysis, LA-I, MM. Writing – Original Draft, PC. Writing – Review & Editing, PC, JL, AM. Visualization, LA-I, MM, LG-G, PC. Funding Acquisition, PC, JL, AM. Resources, PC, JL. Supervision, PC, JL.

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FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1. ERK binding at the *MYC* promoter. A) Depiction of the presence of ERK binding sites (ERK boxes) at the *MYC* promoters from human, rat and mouse. B-D) Agonist-induced ERK recruitment to *MYC* promoter fragments containing ERK boxes, as determined by ChIP in the indicated cell types, under starvation or stimulated for 30 min with 10% FCS or 100 ng/ml EGF; or with IFN γ 1000 UI/ml for 24 h as indicated. E) Right panel: NRAS^{Q61}-induced ERK recruitment to the *MYC* promoter in UR61 cells as determined by ChIP in control or dexamethasone-treated cells (100 nM, 4 hrs). Left panel: dexamethasone-induced expression of NRAS^{Q61} and ERK activation in UR61 cells. B-E: data shows average \pm SD from 3 (B,C) or two (D,E) independent experiments. P values: * p<0.05; **** p<0.001 by two-tailed unpaired Student T-Test.

Figure 2. Induction of *MYC* expression by nuclear ERK. A) *MYC* mRNA (left panel) and protein (right panel) levels evoked by treatment with FCS (10%, 45 min) in the presence of U0126 pretreatment (10 μ M, 30 min) before FCS addition. st= serum-starved B) *MYC* protein expression in response to ERK depletion in growing ERK-less MEFs after DMSO or 4-HT treatment (0.6 μ M) for the indicated days. C) *MYC* mRNA expression in starved ERK-depleted ERK-less MEFs stimulated (+) with EGF (50 ng/ml ,45 min). D) *MYC* mRNA levels in 293T cells transfected with the indicated ERK2 constructs (1 μ g) under quiescence. E) *MYC* protein levels under quiescence (Q) or growing (GR) conditions. ev= empty vector. F) *MYC* promoter response to nuclear ERK. Luciferase expression under the regulation of the depicted promoter fragments, in starved 293T cells cotransfected with vector or ERK2-NLS (1 μ g). A,C,D,F: data shows mean \pm SD from 4 independent experiments. P values: * p<0.05; ** p<0.01; *** p<0.005; **** p<0.001, by two-tailed unpaired Student T-Test.

Figure 3. ERK interaction with CDK9. A) ERK coimmunoprecipitation (IP) with the indicated CDKs, in growing 293T cells transfected with vector (c) or ERK2-NLS (1 μ g each). B) In vivo association of ERK2 with CDK9 in starved or EGF-stimulated (100 ng/ml, 30 min) HeLa cells, as determined by Proximity Ligation Assays (PLA). Scale bar = 10 μ m. C) Endogenous CDK9 coimmunoprecipitation (IP) with NLS-ERK1 or the indicated NLS-ERK2 mutant forms, transfected (1 μ g each) in 293T cells. ev= empty vector; TL = total lysates; PI = pre-immune serum.

Figure 4. Functional consequences of CDK9–ERK interaction. A) Pull-down of ERK2 from 293T lysates, using fusion proteins expressing GST plus the indicated CDK9 fragments. Asterisks indicate the presence of canonical ERK binding sites. B) ERK2 coimmunoprecipitation (IP) with the indicated FLAG-tagged CDK9 mutants transfected (1 μ g each) in 293T cells (proliferating). C) FLAG-CDK9 coimmunoprecipitation (IP) with the indicated HA-tagged ERK2-NLS mutant forms, cotransfected (1 μ g each) in 293T cells. D) Luciferase expression under the regulation of the MYC promoter in response to the indicated constructs (1 μ g each) in starved 293T cells E) Pol II CTD Ser 2 phosphorylation assayed in starved 293T cells transfected with ERK2-NLS (1 μ g) where indicated (+), in which CDK9 expression was down-regulated using siRNAs where indicated (+). F) In vitro kinase assay using purified CDK9/Cyclin K complex, in the presence of the indicated, purified ERK2 mutant forms. GST-CTD and myelin basic protein (MBP) were used as substrates. Bars show mean from five independent experiments. TL = total lysates.

Figure 5. MYC expression dependence on ERK–CDK9 interaction. A) Regulation of MYC mRNA and protein levels in HeLa cells transfected with ERK2-NLS (1 μ g) where indicated (+), in which CDK9 expression was down-regulated using siRNAs where indicated (+). Data shows mean \pm SD from 3 independent experiments. B) MYC expression in 293T CDK9-silenced cells under serum stimulation (10%, 45 min). Data shows mean \pm SD from 4 independent experiments. C) Rescue of

MYC expression in CDK9-knock-down cells transfected with the indicated CDK9 mutant forms (1 μ g each). D) MYC mRNA levels in quiescent cells transfected with the indicated ERK2 mutant forms (1 μ g each). Data shows mean \pm SD from 3 independent experiments. E) MYC protein levels in quiescent 293T cells transfected with the indicated ERK2 mutant forms (1 μ g each). P values: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.005$; **** $p < 0.001$, by two-tailed unpaired Student T-Test.

Figure 6. ERK tethers CDK9 to the MYC promoter. A) ChIP using anti-CDK9 and anti-ERK2 antibodies on the *MYC* gene in HeLa cells. The immunoprecipitated DNA was subjected to qPCR for the indicated regions of *MYC* and the results are expressed relative to the highest signal. B) ChIP performed as in A, in ERK-less MEFs treated with DMSO or 4-HT (0.6 μ M, 7 days). A,B data shows mean \pm SD from 3 independent experiments. P values: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.005$; **** $p < 0.001$, by two-tailed unpaired Student T-Test.

Figure 7. ERK insert region tethers CDK9 to the MYC promoter. A) *MYC* mRNA levels in quiescent HeLa cells transfected with the indicated NLS-ERK2 constructs (1 μ g each). ev, empty vector. B) Left panel: Luciferase expression under the regulation of the MYC promoter in response to the indicated constructs (1 μ g each) in starved 293T cells. Right panel: expression levels of the HA-tagged ERK and FLAG-tagged CDK9 constructs. Data shows mean \pm SD from 4 independent experiments. C) Rescue of MYC expression in CDK9Knock-downn cells transfected with the indicated CDK9 constructs (1 μ g each). D) Proliferation of NIH3T3 cells expressing the indicated CDK9 constructs. A,D: Data shows mean \pm SD from 3 independent experiments. P values: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$, by two-tailed unpaired Student T-Test.

Figure 8. A model for CDK9 recruitment to the MYC promoter by ERK. At the *MYC* promoter ERK binds to DNA through its insert region, anchoring CDK9 therein by interacting via ERK CD

domain with CDK9 D-domain. ERK does not activate CDK9 kinase activity, but brings it to the proximity of RNA Pol II boosting transcription.

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

A

B

C

D

F

E

FIGURE 3

A

C

B

FIGURE 4

FIGURE 5

FIGURE 6**A**

FIGURE 7

FIGURE 8

